

THE SOCIAL NECESSITY OF CITIZENS' PARTICIPATION IN MAINTAINING PUBLIC ORDER

Kushbakov Shohrukh Hasan ugli

Senior Lecturer of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal
Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Captain

Rasulov Dilshodbek Utkir ugli

Cadet of the Academy of the Ministry of Internal
Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Private
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Abstract: This article examines foreign experiences and opinions of legal scholars regarding the social necessity of citizen participation in maintaining public order. The author has developed proposals and recommendations in this field.

Keywords: citizen, public order, public safety, public places.

Today, the development of our state in all spheres is opening up numerous opportunities for our citizens. It is no secret that the changes taking place in various areas of society are being implemented directly through the active participation of citizens. Control over the activities of all state bodies implementing state policy is carried out not only through legislative acts but also through public oversight. In this regard, citizens' participation in maintaining order in public places serves as evidence of our point. Let's first consider what places are called public places. By public space, we can understand areas, buildings, structures and their parts, as well as transport communications, which are accessible to everyone without barriers (or for staying) or are designed to meet various needs of citizens.

According to world scientists, public places are divided into 3 types:

1) Permanent public places - these are public places where citizens are permanently present or have the possibility of permanent stay, are not defined by working hours, and have objects of permanent residence of citizens. These include transport highways, streets, residential areas, neighborhoods, districts, territories of small districts, airports, and railway and bus stations.

2) Temporary public places include areas where citizens are temporarily present or have the possibility of temporary stay, are defined by working hours, and where there are no objects of permanent residence for citizens.

3) One-time public places are venues for mass public events and facilities intended for mass public, agricultural, and other events (ceremonial and religious) and specific territorial objects.

The continuity of our current peaceful and prosperous life is primarily expressed in how the political system in the country is managed and how citizens respond to such policies. We know that it is the duty of each of us to maintain peace in society. However, unfortunately, actions that negatively affect the development of our state and disturb the peace of citizens still continue.

European scholars have identified the following types of public order violations:

Consuming alcoholic beverages in public places (except in specially designated areas), being intoxicated in public places;

Participating in gambling for money, items, and other valuables in yards, terraces, parks, gardens, markets, public transport, beaches, and other public places (except for specially designated areas);

Insulting citizens in public places and other similar actions that disrupt public order and disturb the peace;

Climbing onto the steps and buffers of freight trains, commuter trains, and long-distance trains;

Crossing streets and railways at unauthorized locations;

Disturbing the peace by singing loudly or playing musical instruments (including the use of power tools for apartment renovations);

Misusing fire escapes, roofs, awnings, and basements of buildings;

Burning garbage near houses, setting fires near buildings, in forest plantations, and in forests;

Swimming in prohibited areas, rivers, and ponds;

Picking flowers from lawns and flowerbeds, collecting protected wild plants, damaging or destroying green spaces;

Damaging railway, aviation, and motor transport equipment, signaling and communication devices, transported equipment, containers, and other property;

Throwing stones and other objects at trains; placing items on railway tracks; entering restricted areas of air, water, and rail transport;

Storing household and industrial waste in unauthorized areas; parking trucks between residential buildings and in courtyards; driving on pedestrian paths; parking on lawns and playgrounds;

Violating rules for pet care and walking;

Entering stands, sports grounds, running tracks, and other areas designated for sports and entertainment events, competitions, or other activities, as well as actions that interfere with the conduct of these events;

Using objects that create noise and disturb spectators or participants of sports and entertainment events, as well as using barriers, lighting equipment, platforms for television filming, and auxiliary structures for unauthorized purposes;

Shouting insults that demean the dignity of organizers, performers, and spectators at sports and entertainment events;

Organizing processions on streets, squares, and other public places after sports and entertainment events that interfere with normal traffic flow or disrupt public order, among others.

From the above-mentioned examples, it can be said that the regulation of such disorders, which can currently occur in all areas without the participation of citizens, creates new types of difficulties and problems. Therefore, it is necessary to instill in citizens a desire to maintain public order and instill in their minds ideas of love for the Motherland, humanity, honesty, and brotherhood, instead of feelings of indifference and distrust of society. Because many cases of disorder and violations, as well as crime, remain undisclosed precisely because citizens are indifferent, unwilling to help others, or don't want to waste their time. This creates a number of problems not only in crime prevention, but also in their detection and elimination. In this regard, Russian scholar Melnikov Oleg Yurevich in his scientific work identified legal and social protection as a factor that encourages citizens to participate in the protection of public order.[1]

As is known, systematic measures have been taken to address this type of problem in the judicial and legal system, and this process continues to this day. An example of this is the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-2833 of March 14, 2017 "On Measures to Further Improve the System of Crime Prevention and Combating Crime" [2] and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers "On Approving the Regulation on the Procedure for Stimulating the Active Participation of Citizens and Public Organizations in Crime Prevention and Combating Crime," issued to ensure the implementation of this resolution, as well as to further strengthen the role of citizens and public organizations in crime prevention and combating [3]

The resolution establishes a procedure for rewarding citizens for their participation in crime prevention and combating crime, according to which citizens and public organizations can be rewarded if there is one of the following grounds:

- prevention or suppression of an administrative offense that is planned or committed intentionally;
- prevention of the commission of a crime as a result of informing law enforcement agencies about the crime being prepared;
- assist law enforcement agencies in stopping intentional crime and its full disclosure;
- disclosure of a crime as a result of identifying evidence that contributes to its disclosure or providing information about the persons who committed it or their whereabouts in respect of an undisclosed crime;
- in accordance with the law, report the hiding address of the person declared wanted, assist law enforcement agencies in his detention;
- identification of a missing person on the basis of his information;
- active participation and direct implementation of propaganda and propaganda activities in the field of crime prevention and combating crime among the population;
- implementation of proposals and initiatives to eliminate the causes and conditions that contribute to the commission of crimes.

Also, the resolution stipulates that proposals for the stimulation of citizens and public organizations shall be implemented by the bodies directly carrying out the prevention of offenses by submitting proposals to the republican and territorial interdepartmental commissions for the prevention of offenses and the fight against crime on the stimulation of citizens and public organizations. It is planned to attach a protocol on an administrative offense, a decision to initiate a criminal case, as well as a decision of the prosecutor's office, investigative, inquiry and pre-investigation bodies or a court ruling on the cancellation of the search in relation to the detained wanted person.

On April 12, 2018, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed the Law "On Public Control" [4]. The main purpose of this law is to regulate relations in the field of organization and implementation of public control over the activities of state bodies and institutions. The document provides for the participation of citizens and media representatives in the inspection and monitoring of the activities of state bodies. According to the law, subjects of public control include citizens, citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and the media. The activities of state bodies, in particular law enforcement and supervisory bodies, and their officials, have been identified as objects of public control.

In connection with the implementation of the State Program for the Implementation of the Action Strategy in Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of Active Investments and Social Development," approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5635 of January 17, 2019, and in order to effectively organize the activities of assistants to prevention (senior) inspectors for public order protection to provide practical assistance to internal affairs bodies in the field of crime prevention and combating crime, the Cabinet of Ministers [7]

The Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, considering the report of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the implementation in the first quarter of 2022 of the State Program for the implementation of the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026 in the "Year of Honoring Human Dignity and Active Neighborhood," noted that the government has taken a number of organizational and practical measures to ensure the systematic and high-quality implementation of the State Program [8].

In addition, an analysis of the work carried out within the framework of the priorities of the State Program over the past period, as well as the noted important statistical indicators, showed that significant results have been achieved in ensuring the implementation of reforms in the economic and social sphere, increasing the level of comprehensive development of the regions of the republic. The fact that 6,822 "Fidokor yoshlar" public patrol groups have been established to ensure the peace and security of mahallas as part of all these measures, also shows once again that the participation of our citizens in maintaining public order is a social necessity for our state.

"It is known that social tension in society sharply intensifies during emergencies: natural disasters, major accidents and catastrophes, epidemics, mass massacres, socio-economic and political crises, terrorist acts. In such situations, the existence of public structures that contribute to the protection of law and order and the elimination of the consequences of emergencies is vitally important.

These factors necessitate the search for and formalization of additional mechanisms for maintaining public order, including the creation of public or public-state organizations of citizens for the protection of public order.

In modern conditions, it is necessary to actively involve the public in creating conditions for citizens to provide comprehensive assistance to the internal affairs bodies in protecting public order and ensuring law and order. [9]

Scientists Y.Y. Kyle and S.V. Yepinina, who conducted research on this topic, analyzed the mechanism of citizen participation in maintaining public order in Great Britain, the United States, Spain, Norway, and other countries.

According to them, the more active the participation of citizens in the activities of the public administration system, that is, the more widely citizens are involved in public affairs, the more successfully the political and economic spheres will develop [10].

It should be noted that the participation of citizens in maintaining public order is primarily important in determining the measures of this participation, methods of participation, and forms of interaction between the authorities and the population.[11] If we analyze the legal regulation of citizen participation in maintaining public order in Uzbekistan within the framework of current legislation, it can be seen that this type of activity is not regulated separately at the legislative level.

Today, most of the crimes committed on the streets and in public places are attributed to cafes and bars, nightclubs and restaurants. Based on this, it is advisable to introduce a mechanism called "Active Citizen." In particular, according to it, the head of each entertainment facility (café, bar) in the territory, using the status of a legal entity, on the basis of his order, assigns one of his employees as a person responsible for maintaining public order on the territory of the facility. The main task of this responsible person - "Active Citizen" is to be in constant contact with the bodies responsible for ensuring public safety, attached to the territory, and to appeal to eliminate any illegal actions committed on the territory of the object, as well as the causes and conditions for their commission. [12]

Furthermore, when studying the legislation of Belarus, Ukraine, Russia, and Israel regarding the regulation of relations related to the preservation of public order and the participation of citizens in it within the framework of law, it can be seen that these relations are regulated within the framework of law within the legislative system of these countries [13].

Our country is implementing numerous reforms aimed at further increasing the participation of citizens in maintaining public order. As an example, the Concept of Public Safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted as ANNEX 1 to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-27 of November 29, 2021, states that "ensuring public safety is carried out in cooperation with state bodies and organizations, citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, public associations, citizens,

and the media." The concept also divides the public safety system into entities that ensure public safety and participate in it, where citizens are included as entities involved in ensuring public safety. In addition, the Concept clearly defines the powers of all subjects, defines the procedure for encouraging non-governmental non-profit organizations and citizens who actively participate in ensuring public safety as an important condition for the tasks of the Cabinet of Ministers, which also shows how important it is to ensure the participation of citizens in ensuring public safety and public order. [14]

In conclusion, it can be said that the human rights function of the state is not only the creation of a system of law enforcement and other state bodies for the protection of public order, but also the formation of a favorable legal framework and organizational and technical conditions for the independent protection of citizens. Therefore, in modern conditions, the most important incentive factor for involving citizens in the protection of public order and a necessary condition for the activities of law enforcement public associations is the establishment of special measures of legal and social protection. To do this, we must first create and ensure the social and legal protection of our citizens, which arises as a result of their participation, before introducing their active participation in maintaining public order. It should also be noted that one of the most common forms of public-state cooperation presented by the internal affairs bodies is the institution of citizen participation in the protection of public order. The effectiveness of its operation largely depends on the level of regulation in the legislation and the regulation of the basic concepts, principles, forms of such participation, the status of persons involved in law enforcement, including guarantees, benefits and compensations. Accordingly, the expansion of public participation in the prevention and elimination of offenses, the encouragement of reporting offenses, will contribute to the reduction of offenses in the country and ensure the rule of law.

Furthermore, it would not be an exaggeration to say that the participation of citizens in maintaining public order has become a social necessity of state policy. In our time, when human rights and freedoms are being ensured and broad opportunities are being created for citizens, the attention of the world community is focused on our state's policy in the field of human rights. This requires government agencies to exercise caution in maintaining public order and working with citizens. Therefore, it is crucial to ensure the participation of our citizens in maintaining public order across all spheres of society. However, to prevent such participation from creating difficulties for citizens, it is

necessary to strengthen their legal protection and appropriately reward the results of their participation to encourage continued involvement. To this end, first and foremost, reviewing and adopting the draft law "On the Participation of Citizens in the Maintenance of Public Order" will further develop the system of ensuring public safety and maintaining public order, which is considered the main direction of state policy today.

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